

Kinetics of Bromine Addition to Chalkones Part II. Linear Free Energy Relationship

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The rates of bromination of chalkone and its eight substituted derivatives have been measured in acetic acid. The thermodynamic parameters have been computed. The rate constants give better correlation against σ^+ than with σ , with $\rho^+ = -1.0$. A quantitative separation of inductive, resonance and steric effects have been attempted. A simple mechanistic scheme is developed basing upon the linear free energy relationship.

Kinetic studies of the addition of bromine to chalkones in methanol, nitrobenzene and benzene have been earlier reported by us¹.

In the present investigation, the kinetic studies of the addition of bromine to a variety of chalkone derivatives have been carried out in acetic acid containing constant quantity of sodium acetate in order to complement our previous investigation and to throw further light on the mechanism of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetic acid was purified as described earlier². The bromine used was of 'Analar' quality. The chalkones were prepared and purified by the method of Nayak, Nayak, Sabat and Rout³. The method of rate measurement and calculation of rate constants were similar as described earlier. The measured rate constants were all accurate to within 2-3% by agreement between duplicate runs. The activation energy was calculated within an accuracy of ± 0.5 K.Cal/mole. The rate constants for various substituents together with the value of the energy of activation is described in Table 1.

Effect of substituent on rate: The rate data for the electrophilic bromine addition (in presence of sodium acetate it is the electrophilic rate⁴) for various substituted chalkones are noted in Table 1. The reaction rate is enhanced by electron donating groups in the phenyl nucleus of the chalkone molecule and the converse is true for electron withdrawing groups, and the order of reactivity of the substituents is

Energy of activation: It is evident from Table 1 that electron withdrawing groups increase the energy of activation and electron donating groups retard it. The substituent effects upon energy of activation conform to the following

TABLE 1

Values of specific reaction rate and energy of activation for substituted chalkones
in acetic acid containing M/40 sodium acetate

[Reactants] = M/80

Name of the substituents	$k \times 10^3 \text{ lit. mole}^{-1}\text{sec.}^{-1}$							E in k.cal/mole
	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°	
Unsubstituted	—	—	10.59	16.76	23.10	31.49	—	12.40
3-NO ₂ -	—	—	—	2.71	4.80	8.69	18.73	22.70
4-NO ₂ -	—	—	—	2.35	3.89	6.86	10.05	23.00
2-NO ₂	—	—	—	2.00	3.41	6.12	9.85	23.56
3-Cl-	—	—	3.08	5.12	5.65	13.15	18.50	17.20
4-Cl-	—	—	8.04	9.12	12.81	18.81	—	13.60
2-Cl-	—	—	4.80	7.07	7.84	14.51	—	15.50
3-Br-	—	—	2.58	4.46	9.48	14.01	—	20.70
4-CH ₃ -	14.5	18.0	19.4	22.30	—	—	—	5.30

A plot of $\log PZ$ against $1/\sqrt{E}$ values gave a straight line, showing that the reaction obeys the Fairclough and Hinshelwood relationship⁵.

Linear free-energy relationship: The values of $\log k/k$ (chalkone) were found to correlate reasonably well ($r = 0.966$, $s = 0.230$) with σ , substituent constants⁶ ($\rho = -0.94$), but considerably better ($r = 0.988$, $s = 0.016$) with σ^+ scale, yielding a ρ value of similar magnitude ($\rho^+ = -1.0$). The negative value of ρ signifies that electron donating groups enhance the reaction rate. These results are consistent with an electrophilic attack in which significant conjugation with the phenyl group of the chalkone molecule is developed at the transition state. The above ρ value can be compared directly with the value obtained in our previous work ($\rho = -1.8$) for analogous bromination in methanol. This considerably more negative value shows that substituent effects on the rate of bromination is more pronounced in methanol than in acetic acid.

A quantitative separation of Inductive, Resonance and Steric effects: The individual contributions due to inductive and resonance effects of a substituent have been determined by the method given by Taft and Lewis^{8,9,10}. The resonance interaction energies of meta- and para-substituents have been evaluated by using the expression¹¹

$\Delta\Delta F_m = -2.303 RT.R_m$; $\Delta\Delta F_p = -2.303 RT.R_p$ respectively. The results are listed in Table 2.

The negative value of $\Delta\Delta F_p$ for the methyl group indicates that there is greater resonance interaction of this group in the transition state than in the reactant state¹¹. The carbon atom adjacent to the phenyl group of the chalkone molecule bears a positive charge in the transition state and this positive charge gets stabilised by the methyl group at para-position

TABLE 2

Values of the inductive effect, resonance effect and meta- and para- resonance interaction energy

Substituent	-CH ₃	-Cl	-NO ₂
<i>I</i>	-0.0615	-0.5787	-0.7754
<i>R_m</i>	—	-0.0643	-0.0159
<i>R_p</i>	-1.0642	-0.3142	-0.0778
$\Delta\Delta F_m$ K.Cal/mole	—	-0.09	-0.02
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ K.Cal/mole	-0.011	-0.45	-1.500
δE_s	—	-0.11	-0.318
$\Delta\Delta F_s$ K.Cal/mole	—	-0.15	-0.45

I = Inductive effect.

R = Resonance effect.

$\Delta\Delta F_m$ = Meta resonance interaction energy.

$\Delta\Delta F_p$ = Para resonance interaction energy.

of the chalkone molecule. The $\Delta\Delta F_p$ value for the nitro group is positive which indicates that it destabilises the transition state¹¹.

The steric effect of the ortho-substituents has been calculated by using the following equation as suggested by Taft¹², $\log k_{ortho}/k_{(unsubstituted)} = I + R_p - (\delta E_s)$ and steric interactive energy has been calculated from the equation¹²

$$\Delta\Delta F_S = -2.303RT (\delta E_S)$$

The results are described in Table 2.

The rates of *ortho*-nitro and *ortho*-chloro chalkones are slower than the corresponding *p*-substituents. Thus both the chloro and nitro groups cause steric hindrance on the transition state and hence the rate decreases. This is further confirmed from the negative value of the steric interaction energies ($\Delta\Delta F_S$ values).

Relative rates of ethyl cinnamate with chalkone: The rate of bromination of ethyl cinnamate has been measured in acetic acid containing *M*/40 sodium acetate. The *k* value at 30° was computed to be 2.75×10^{-3} lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ (concentration of reactants being *M*/80). It is seen that chalkone adds bromine more rapidly than ethyl cinnamate (about four fold rise of *k* value). When electrophilic reactivity is required by the reagent, the phenyl group (in benzoyl) appears to be more polarisable than the ethoxy group¹³.

Mechanism of the reaction. The value of ρ^+ (-1.0) for bromine addition to chalkone is quite low in comparison with the ρ value ($\rho = -4.21$) for the bromination of substituted styrene¹⁴, and ($\rho = -4.54$) for the solvolysis of phenyldimethyl-carbinyl chloride¹⁵, where a fully developed benzylic carbonium ion-like activated complex is involved in the slow step.

The value larger than -3 has been suggested by various workers¹⁵ for a fairly large degree of carbonium ion character in the activated complex. Consequently a partially bridged resonance stabilised three-membered-ring activated complex may be suggested where the charge is delocalised between C_α , C_β and the bromine which may be represented as follows :

The above picture of the transition state is further confirmed from the negative $\Delta\Delta F_p^\ddagger$ value for the methyl group which means that it stabilises the transition state¹¹ by electron donation.

Similar type of three membered ring activated complex has also been suggested by us for the methoxy mercuration¹⁶, Tl^{+3} oxidation¹⁷, peroxidation¹⁸ and Cr(VI) oxidation¹⁹ of chalcone.

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